

<https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2025.01.26>

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:40BA465B-1894-438B-9B6B-7219713A9598>

● ***Anomala tingis*, a new species related to *A. corrugata* Bates, 1866 from southern China (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Rutelinae)**

Ming-Zhi ZHAO

Leibniz Institute for the Analysis of Biodiversity Change, Museum A. Koenig, Adenauerallee 127, 53113 Bonn, Germany;

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3158-6177>; zhaomzhai@gmail.com

Abstract: A new ruteline scarab beetle, *Anomala tingis* sp. nov., is described based on material collected from three provinces in southern China. The only morphologically similar species, *A. corrugata* Bates, 1866, is compared, along with new geographic data. Color images and a distribution map are provided for both species.

Keywords: Leaf chafers, new record, new taxon, Scarabaeoidea, taxonomy

● **中国南部筛翅异丽金龟 *Anomala corrugata* Bates, 1866 一近缘新种——网翅异丽金龟 *Anomala tingis* sp. nov. (鞘翅目：金龟科：丽金龟亚科)**

赵明智

莱布尼茨生物多样性变化分析所，柯尼希博物馆，阿登纳大街 127 号，波恩 53113，德国

摘要：本文描述一个采自中国南部的异丽金龟新种，即网翅异丽金龟 *Anomala tingis* sp. nov.，并与该新种在形态上已知的唯一近似物种筛翅异丽金龟 *A. corrugata* Bates, 1866 进行了对比，同时增加了后者的地理分布范围，提供了二者的形态图和分布图。

关键词：丽金龟，新纪录，新分类单元，金龟总科，分类学

Citation: Zhao M-Z 2025: *Anomala tingis*, a new species related to *A. corrugata* Bates, 1866 from southern China (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Rutelinae). *The Indochina Entomologist*, 1 (26): 253–260. [赵明智 2025: 中国南部筛翅异丽金龟 *Anomala corrugata* Bates, 1866 一近缘新种——网翅异丽金龟 *Anomala tingis* sp. nov. (鞘翅目：金龟科：丽金龟亚科). 中南半岛昆虫学家, 1 (26): 253–260.]

<https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2025.01.26>

Accepted by Hao XU: 16.I.2025; published online: 16.I.2025

Copyright Ming-Zhi ZHAO. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CCBY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

● Introduction

The genus *Anomala* Samouelle, 1819 is amongst the most diverse genera in the tribe Anomalini Streubel, 1839 and in the subfamily Rutelinae Macleay, 1819 with over 1000 recorded taxa (Krajčič 2007). It also counts about half of the known diversity of Chinese leaf chafer (Lu *et al.* 2023). Compared to the similar genera *Callistethus* Blanchard, 1851 and *Mimela* Kirby, 1823, *Anomala* species are typically characterized by the absence of ventral thoracic processes. Since such processes evolved independently in various Anomalina groups (Zorn 2011; Filippini *et al.* 2015), to simply rely on these character states makes *Anomala* a non-monophyletic entity (Jameson *et al.* 2003; Ramírez-Ponce & Morón 2009).

Anomala corrugata Bates, 1866 is an enigmatic species from southeastern China. The dorsal surface bears extensive large punctures, and the body shape is ovoid, with elytra widest near apex, whereas widest around middle in most *Anomala* species. Machatschke (1957) grouped *A. corrugata* with *A. viridicostata* Nonfried, 1892. The latter, however, is a member of the *A. spilopecta*-group (sensu Zorn *et al.* 2017) whose parameres are dorsobasally connected by a broad membrane. The sculpture and body shape reminds the author of some *Mimela* species, e.g. *M. holosericea* (Fabricius, 1787), *M. sericea* Ohaus, 1905, and *M. yonaguniensis* Nomura, 1965 despite the missing prosternal process. So far, there seems no related species of it within the genus *Anomala*.

In recent years, the author identified a species morphologically similar to *A. corrugata* among material collected from southern China. After a careful study, it was proved to be new to science and is described here.

● Material and methods

The examination and dissection of specimens, preparation of color plates, and the treatment of labels follow that of Zhao *et al.* (2024). Specimens quoted in the present paper are deposited in the following public or personal collections:

- AHNU Anhui Normal University, Wuhu, China;
- MNHN Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France;
- NMPC National Museum, Praha, Czech Republic;
- SCAU South China Agricultural University, Guangzhou, China;
- SYSU The Museum of Biology, Sun Yat-sen University, Guangzhou, China;
- CCPC Chang-Chin Chen personal collection, Tianjin, China;
- CZPC Carsten Zorn personal collection, Gnoien, Germany;
- SJPC Stanislav Jákl personal collection, Praha, Czech Republic;
- TZPC Zhao-Yang Tang personal collection, Shenzhen, China;
- ZMPC Ming-Zhi Zhao personal collection, Zhuhai, China.

● Taxonomy

Anomala tingis sp. nov. 网翅异丽金龟

<https://zoobank.org/81477275-A366-473C-9DCC-9890E2FCE497>

Figs 1–2, 4–6, 10

Type material. HOLOTYPE. ♂ (SCAU) “CHINA: Guangxi, Fangchenggang City, Naliang Town, Tansan Village [滩散村], 325 m, 2023.IV.17–22, Le Liang leg.”. **PARATYPES** (21♂, 27♀). **Guangxi:** 2♂ (TZPC) “CHINA: Guangxi, Fangchenggang City, Naliang Town, Tansan Village, 325 m, 2023.IV.17–22, Le Liang leg.”; 2♂, 1♀ (ZMPC) “CHINA: Guangxi, Fangchenggang City, Naliang Town, Tansan Village, 325 m, 2023.IV.17–22, Le Liang leg.”; 1♀ (ZMPC) “CHINA: Guangxi, Fangchenggang City, Naliang Town, Tansan Village, 325 m, 2023.IV.26, local leg.”; 1♀ (TZPC) “CHINA: Guangxi, Fangchenggang City, Naliang Town, Tansan Village, 325 m, 2023.V.1, local leg.”; 1♀ (ZMPC)

“CHINA: Guangxi, Fangchenggang City, Naliang Town, Tansan Village, 325 m, 2023.V.2, local leg.”; 2♀ (TZPC)
 “CHINA: Guangxi, Fangchenggang City, Naliang Town, Tansan Village, 325 m, 2023.V.6, local leg.”; 1♂, 1♀ (TZPC)
 “CHINA: Guangxi, Fangchenggang City, Naliang Town, Tansan Village, 325 m, 2023.V.7, local leg.”; 2♀ (TZPC)
 “CHINA: Guangxi, Fangchenggang City, Naliang Town, Tansan Village, 325 m, 2023.V.11, local leg.”; 1♀ (ZMPC)
 “CHINA: Guangxi, Fangchenggang City, Naliang Town, Tansan Village, 325 m, 2023.V.14, local leg.”; 1♀ (ZMPC)
 “CHINA: Guangxi, Fangchenggang City, Naliang Town, Tansan Village, 325 m, 2023.V.15, local leg.”; 1♂ (ZMPC)
 “CHINA: Guangxi, Fangchenggang City, Naliang Town, Tansan Village, 325 m, 2023.V.19, local leg.”; 1♂, 1♀ (TZPC)
 “CHINA: Guangxi, Fangchenggang City, Naliang Town, Tansan Village, 325 m, 2023.V.20, local leg.”; 1♂, 1♀ (ZMPC)
 “CHINA: Guangxi, Fangchenggang City, Naliang Town, Tansan Village, 325 m, 2023.V.28, local leg.”; 2♂, 1♀ (ZMPC)
 “CHINA: Guangxi, Fangchenggang City, Naliang Town, Tansan Village, 325 m, 2023.V.30, local leg.”; 1♂ (ZMPC)
 “CHINA: Guangxi, Shangsi, Shiwandashan Mts. 495 m, 2019.IV.19, at light, Bo-Yan Li leg.”; 2♀ (ZMPC) “CHINA: Guangxi, Shangsi, Shiwandashan Mts. 434 m, 2019.IV.21, at light, Bo-Yan Li leg.”; **Guangdong:** 1♂ (SYSU) “Guangdong, Fengkai, Heishiding light trap 2.VI.2011 Mu-Chun Cheng, Jun-Lei Liao leg.”; 1♀ (SYSU) “Guangdong, Fengkai, He’erkou [河儿口] 2010-v-8 light trap Hai-Dong Chen, Hong-Sheng Wu, Yong-Jun Li, Hong Pang leg.”; **Hainan:** 1♂ (CCPC) “Hainan, Mt. Limushan, Mengxiantu [梦仙图] 800/m 23.IV.2009 Xiao-Yu Zhu leg.”; 1♀ (CCPC) “Hainan, Mt. Limushan, Mengxiantu 800/m 27.IV.2009 Xiao-Yu Zhu leg.”; 2♂ (ZMPC) “CHINA-Hainan, Mt. Limushan, Sanquling [三曲岭], 600 m, 2022.IV.23 Yu-Cheng Zheng leg.”; 1♀ (ZMPC) “CHINA: Hainan, Qiongzong, Mt. Limu, 19.16996908N, 109.74695635E 627 m, 2024.IV.8-13, at light, Yu-Zhou Huang, Xiao-Han Ye, Ze-Chuan Li leg.”; 1♂, 8♀ (ZMPC) “CHINA: Hainan, Lingshui, Mt. Diaoluo, 18.72268866N, 109.78222715E 925 m, 2024.IV.14-15, at light, Yu-Zhou Huang, Xiao-Han Ye, Ze-Chuan Li leg.”.

Description. Male. Body shape elongated ovoid, moderately convex.

Color. Generally yellowish brown, frontoclypeal suture, eye canthus, frons (except for very narrow anterior portion), vertex, disc of pronotum (except for narrow anterior and posterior and wide lateral marginal portions), scutellum, elytra, pygidium (except for posterior marginal portions) and all tibiae grass green; dorsal surface and tibiae metallic; protibial teeth, all robust setae on legs dark brown.

Head. Labrum weakly produced under ventral margin of clypeus. Frontal face of clypeus vertical, with minute setae along its ventral margin and on lateral portions. Greatest length/width of clypeus = 1/2.7, subtrapezoidal, anterior margin nearly straight, anterior corners rounded; anterior margin moderately reflexed; surface densely and finely rugopunctate. Frontoclypeal suture straight, hardly elevated. Frons with dense and large, irregularly arranged and confluent punctures, vertex with dense and small punctures. Interocular distance/maximum head width = 0.7. Length of antennal club approximately 0.7 times as long as combined length of antennomeres 1–6. Inner margin of eye with several moderately long setae.

Pronotum. Sides gently arched and weakly convergent anteriorly in posterior half, straight and strongly convergent anteriorly in anterior half. Anterior angle acute and protruding, posterior angle broadly rounded and not protruding. Anterior and posterior marginal line broadly interrupted in the middle, lateral marginal lines complete. Disc with very dense and large punctures, irregularly arranged and frequently connected, interspace between punctures raised and irregular. Lateral margin with a few long setae.

Scutellum triangular, sides slightly convex. Glabrous, disc with dense and small punctures, as well as microsculpture.

Elytra. The whole disc bearing very dense and large punctures, punctures near humeral protuberance small; intervals unrecognizable, each elytron bearing five slightly elevated and smooth costae from suture to lateral portion, costa 4 absent in basal third, space between costae 1 and 2 widest, other costae equally spaced. Humeral and apical protuberances moderately prominent. Lateral carina distinctly expanded in basal four fifths, widest along metacoxa, with dense, fine and transverse striolation. Epipleura with a row of rather sparse and minute setae, denser near base. Marginal membrane broad, appearing slightly behind the anterior margin of metacoxa.

FIGURES 1–3. Habitus of *Anomala* spp.: 1, 2 *A. tingis* sp. nov. holotype male, in dorsal and lateral views 3 *A. corrugata* male (Fujian, Puchanshan), in dorsal view. Scale bar = 5 mm.

FIGURES 4–9. Aedeagus of *Anomala* spp. in dorsal, right lateral and ventral views: 4–6 *A. tingis* sp. nov. holotype 7–9 *A. corrugata* (Fujian, Puchanshan). Scale bar = 2 mm.

Abdomen. Propygidium hidden by elytra. Pygidium weakly convex in lateral view, surface with dense punctures, interspaces with rather dense and fine microsculpture, with sparse and long setae preapically and a transverse row along apical margin. Abdominal ventrites not carinate laterally, punctures sparse and transverse, more rounded and denser laterally; ventrites 2–5 each with a transverse and sparse row of short setae, long along midline, the row of ventrite 6 present at posterior margin and with long setae.

Ventral thoracic surface. Hypomeron with sparse, large and annulated punctures each bearing a short seta. Ventral mesothoracic surface with dense, transverse and small punctures each bearing a minute and recumbent seta. Ventral metathoracic surface with dense, large and shallow annulated punctures, sometimes confluent laterally, with dense and long setae, medial portions with rather sparse and small punctures as well as few minute setae. Metacoxae punctate as lateral metasternum but glabrous.

Legs. Protibia bidentate, both teeth distinct; apical tooth extending to anterior margin of protarsomere 2. Inner spur inserted at distal third of protibia. Inner protarsal claw and outer mesotarsal claw split apically, lower branch three times wider than upper branch in protarsal claw and two times in mesotarsal claw, both branches equal in length; lower margin of lower branch of inner protarsal claw not convex, forming a notch internobasally; outer metatarsal claw slightly longer than inner one. Each tarsomere 5 with an internomedial denticle, that of mesotarsomere 5 smaller. Ventral surface of mesofemur with two longitudinal rows of short to long setae, with additional long setae between the two rows; meso- and metatibiae each bearing two oblique groups of robust setae emerging from a carina, basal fourth with a few fine setae.

Male genitalia. Parameres symmetric, glabrous, narrower at apical half. Ventral plate with a truncate and deflected apical margin.

Female. Antennal club slightly shorter. Pygidium more triangular in shape. Apical protibial tooth longer and wider, extending to anterior margin of protarsomere 3, proximal tooth right-angled; inner spur inserted at mid-length of protibia; internomedial protuberance of 5th protarsomere small; protarsomeres distinctly thinner, lower branch of inner protarsal claw two times wider than upper branch, not forming a notch internobasally. Ultimate abdominal ventrite 1.5 times longer than in male medially.

Measurements. Body length: 16.8–18.7 mm for male (holotype 17.1 mm) and 14.7–18.4 mm for female, greatest width: 9.5–10.2 mm for male (holotype 9.7 mm) and 9.2–10.4 mm for female.

Differential diagnosis. *Anomala tingis* sp. nov. is closely allied to *A. corrugata* Bates, 1866. However, the male of the new species has wider tibiae, and the punctures on the dorsal surface are overall more regular than those of *A. corrugata*. Additionally, they can be distinguished by the shape of parameres in lateral view: those of *A. tingis* are narrower in apical half, the apex is more acute, and the ventral concavity is deeper than in *A. corrugata*.

Etymology. *Tingis* is the type genus of the lace bugs, Tingidae. The name is used here as a noun in apposition, referring to the similar dorsal sculpture.

Distribution. China: Guangdong, Guangxi, Hainan.

Anomala corrugata Bates, 1866 筛翅异丽金龟

Figs 3, 7–9, 10

Anomala corrugata Bates, 1866: 343 [type locality: “Formosa”]; Yu *et al.* 1998: 119, 199, pl. 13, fig. 3; Lu & Bai 2020: 104, pl. IX, fig. 9.

Anomala holosericioides Nijima & Kinoshita, 1927: 85, pl. II, fig. 11, pl. III, fig. 9 [type locality: “Formosa: Taihoku”, currently Taipei]; Kobayashi 1984: 17, fig. 2; Yu *et al.* 1998: 199 [synonym]; Lin 2002: 398, fig. 27–565 [record from Fujian, Guangdong, Guangxi].

Type material. 2♂, 2♀ (MNHN) syntypes of *A. corrugata* from Formosa, examined through photos.

Additional material. CHINA: Anhui: 2♂, 2♀ (AHNU) Anhui Prov., Huangshan City, Jiulongfeng [九龙峰],

30.12464359°N, 118.02228679°E, 309 m, 2024.V.22, leg. Hai-Feng Xu, Zafar; **Fujian**: 27♂, 5♀ (CZPC, NMPC) China: Fujian Province, Wuyishan Mts. NNR, Sangang vill. env., 24.V. – 3.VI.2016, 27°45.0'N, 117°40.7'E, 720 m, river valley, wet rock along road, J. Hájek, D. Král, J. Růžička & L. Sekerka lgt.; 1♂ (ZMPC) Fujian, Sanming, Puchan Mt. [普禅山], 2015-VI-30, Zhi-Hao Qi, Zheng Shi leg.; **Guangdong**: 6♂, 3♀ (SYSU) Kwangtung, S. China Taam Yuen Tung [潭源洞] Lin-hsien (District) May 25, 1934. F. K. To; 6♂, 6♀ (SYSU) Kwangtung, S. China Taam Yuen Tung Lin-hsien (District) June 1, 1934. F. K. To; 1♂ (ZMPC) Guangdong, Shixing, Chebaling, 1990.IV.19, Xing Su leg.; **Guangxi**: 5♂, 4♀ (CZPC, SJPC) China, Guangxi, 1200m, Dayao Shan, SE Luzhou, 23°45'N 109°45'E, VI.2005, V. Siniacv leg.; 1♂ (CCPC) Guangxi, Guilin City, Xing'an County, Gaozhai [高寨], 500-600 m, 2013.V.21-23, Y.-F. Hsu leg.; 2♂ (SYSU) Guangxi, Guilin, Maoershan, Tongren-Jiuniutang-Sanjiangyuan [同仁-九牛塘-三江源], top of the mountain, 350-1180-2100 m, 2004.IV.29–V.4, Chun-Tian Zhang; **Hunan**: 1♀ (ZMPC) CHINA: Hunan Prov. Chenzhou City, Guidong Co., Baoxia Vill. [堡下村] 2023.V.21 25° 51' 50" N, 113° 51' 40" E HID light trap, Sun-Bin Huang; **Jiangxi**: 51 ex (SYSU) Jiangxi, Jinggangshan, Xiangzhou [湘洲], 2011-V-31, Li-Jun Yang, Jing-Wei Li leg.; **Zhejiang**: 1♂ (ZMPC) Zhejiang, Jiangshan City, Shuangxikou [双溪口] 400-650 m Xin-Ran Li, Li-Li Wang, Meng Li 2017.5.26-27; 51 ex (ZMPC) Zhejiang, Lishui, Jingning County, 2017.VII.12, light trap, Jing-Kun Zhang leg.

Remarks. *Anomala corrugata* was previously misidentified by Nomura (1965) and Kobayashi (1984). The Japanese name “タイワンサクラコガネ” (Taiwan Sakurakogane) quoted by the two authors refers to *A. siniopyga* Ohaus, 1917 as clarified by Yu *et al.* (1998). Yu *et al.* (1998) also denoted that Miyake *et al.* (1991) synonymized *A. holosericioides* with *A. corrugata*. However, this taxonomic act is not explicitly stated in the work of Miyake *et al.*, where only a misidentification of *A. corrugata* had been discussed. Therefore, Yu *et al.* (1998) represents the first formal treatment of the synonymization. The male genitalia of *A. holosericioides* illustrated by Nijima & Kinoshita (1927) correspond to that of *A. corrugata* from continent, which is further evidence.

Lin (2002) reported this species from Guangdong and Guangxi without specifying precise localities, where both *A. tingis* and *A. corrugata* are presented. The material examined in this paper clarifies the distribution of *A. corrugata* in these two provinces and newly extends its known range to four additional provinces.

Distribution. China: Anhui*, Fujian, Guangdong, Guangxi, Hunan*, Jiangxi*, Taiwan, Zhejiang* (new record each with an asterisk).

FIGURE 10. Map of southeastern China showing the approximate known distribution of *Anomala tingis* sp. nov. (blue star) and *A. corrugata* (red triangle).

● Acknowledgements

The author express his hearty thanks to Mr. Zhao-Yang Tang (Shenzhen), Mr. Chang-Chin Chen (Taoyuan), Mr. Jing-Kun Zhang (Chongqing), Dr. Yu-Chen Zheng (Xiamen), Mr. Yu-Zhou Huang (Changsha), Mr. Xiao-Han Ye (Quzhou), Mr. Ze-Chuan Li (Tai'an), Mr. Bo-Yan Li (Guiyang), Mr. Mr. Zhi-Hao Qi (Nanping), Dr. Sun-Bin Huang (SCAU), Dr. Lu Qiu (Mianyang) for their generous donations of specimens. Thanks are also due to Dr. Carsten Zorn (Gnoien), Dr. Jiří Hájek (NMPC), Dr. Rui-E Nie (AHNU), Mr. Yu Bao (Chizhou) for sharing some records of *A. corrugata*. The author is deeply grateful to Dr. Bin-Lan Zhang for her support during his visit to SYSU and to Dr. Hao Xu (Mianyang) for providing essential literature. Special thanks are extended to Dr. Carsten Zorn and Mr. Fa-Lei Wang (Chongqing) for improving the manuscript.

● References

- Bates HW 1866: On a collection of Coleoptera from Formosa sent home by R. Swinhoe, Esq. H.B.M. Consul, Formosa. *Proceedings of the Scientific Meetings of the Zoological Society of London*, 23: 339–355.
- Filippini V, Galante E & Micó E 2015: The genus *Callistethus* (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Rutelinae) in the Neotropics: new data and new species from Costa Rica. *Arthropod Systematics & Phylogeny*, 73 (2): 199–238.
- Jameson ML, Paucar-Cabrera A & Solis A 2003: Synopsis of the New World genera of Anomalini and description of a new genus from Costa Rica and Nicaragua. *Annals of the entomological Society of America*, 96 (4): 415–432.
- Kobayashi H 1984: Scarabaeidae of Taiwan (10). *Gekkan-Mushi*, 155: 17–20.
- Krajčič M 2007: Checklist of the Scarabaeoidea of the World. 2. Rutelinae (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Rutelinae). *Animma.x, Supplementum*, 4: 1–139.
- Lin P 2002: Rutelidae. In: Huang B-K (Ed) *Fauna of insects of Fujian Province of China. Volume 6*. Fujian Science & Technology Press, Fuzhou, pp. 387–427. [林平 2002: 丽金龟科. 见: 黄邦侃 (主编) 福建昆虫志. 第六卷. 福建科学技术出版社, 福州, pp. 387–427.]
- Lu Y-Y & Bai M 2020: Rutelinae MacLeay, 1819. In: Bai M (Ed) *The Scarabaeoidea of Wuyishan, Fujian, China*. Agricultural Science and Technology Press, Beijing, pp. 96–130. [路园园 & 白明 2020: 丽金龟亚科. 见: 白明 (主编) 武夷山金龟志. 中国农业科学技术出版社, 北京, pp. 96–130.]
- Lu Y-Y, Ding Q, Yang X-K & Bai M 2023: Advances in taxonomy of Chinese Rutelinae. *Journal of Environmental Entomology*, 45 (3): 611–619. [路园园, 丁强, 杨星科 & 白明 2023: 中国丽金龟亚科昆虫分类学研究进展. 环境昆虫学报, 45 (3): 611–619.]
- Machatschke JW 1957: Coleoptera Lamellicornia Fam. Scarabaeidae Subfam. Rutelinae. Zweiter Teil. In: Wytzman PAG (Ed) *Genera insectorum. Fascicule 199 (B)*. Desmet-Verteneuil, Bruxelles, pp. 1–219.
- Miyake Y, Nakamura S & Kojima K 1991: The Scarabaeoidea of Taiwan preserved in Hiwa Museum for Natural History, with description of two new species (Coleoptera: Polyphaga). *Museum Report of the Hiwa Museum of Natural History, Hiroshima*, 29: 1–41.
- Nijijima Y & Kinoshita E 1927: Die Untersuchungen über japanische Melolonthiden III. (Erster Nachtrag der Melolonthiden Japans und ihre Verbreitung). *Research Bulletins of the College Experiment Forest, College of Agriculture, Hokkaido Imperial University (Sapporo)*, 4: 1–95.
- Nomura S 1965: List of some Formosan Coleoptera collected by the member of Lep. Soc. Jap. *Special Bulletin of the Lepidopterological Society of Japan*, 1: 141–146.
- Ramírez-Ponce A & Morón MÁ 2009: Relaciones filogenéticas del género *Anomala* (Coleoptera: Melolonthidae: Rutelinae). *Revista Mexicana de Biodiversidad*, 80 (2): 357–394.
- Yu C-K, Kobayashi H & Chu Y-I 1998: *The Scarabaeidae of Taiwan*. Mu Sheng Company, Taipei, 263 pp. [余清金, 小林裕和 & 朱耀沂 1998: 植食性金龜. 木生昆蟲有限公司, 台北, 263 pp.]
- Zhao M-Z, Zorn C & Liu W-X 2024: Exploring the *Anomala fuscicornata*-complex: discovery of two new species from southern China (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Rutelinae). *Zootaxa*, 5528 (1): 283–299.
- Zorn C 2011: New species of the genus *Anomala* Samouelle from mainland South East Asia and South China (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae:

Rutelinae). *Stuttgarter Beiträge zur Naturkunde A, Neue Serie*, 4: 297–312.

Zorn C, Kobayashi H & Wada K 2017: Notes on the genus *Anomala* Samouelle, 1819 (Coleoptera, Scarabaeidae, Rutelinae) in Vietnam and neighboring regions: eight new species and faunistic records. *Beiträge zur Entomologie*, 67 (2): 325–352.

● Additional information

Author contributions: The author solely contributed to this work.

Conflict of interest: The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

Data availability: All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

Ethical statement: No ethical statement was reported.

Funding: This study was self-funded by the authors.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of *ICE* and/or the editor(s). *ICE* and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.